

RFID-Based Gate Access Control System with PIN Entry

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Abstract— Institutions, with a considerable number of staffs, need to record employee attendance, and also monitor and limit security breaches in the system. The manual process of performing the data logging for employee attendance is inconvenient and time-wasting. Hence, in this work, an automatic access control system and data logging for an institution gate barrier is developed using Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Technology. This system is unique because it combines RFID with Personal Identification Number (PIN) entry for enhanced security. The developed system grants access to authorized users as well as logs the user's details into MySQL data base and eventually a webpage for security administration. Reliability assessment performed gave a reliability of 98% at the gate entry point and 97% at the exit point. The system is convenient, reliable, with components readily available. Possible applications include personal premises, military zone, and premises of government or organisation where high level of security is required.

Keywords— Access control; automatic identification and data capturing; microcontroller; PIN entry; RFID.

I. INTRODUCTION

Institutions with ample staffing require people entering through the University main gate to receive a plastic or metal tag which they must give back on their exit in order to certify and monitor staff and visitor. The process is used for security and monitoring of staff and vehicles coming in and out of the premises. An additional process may require logging of staff and visitor's data such as writing down names, office numbers, time in, and time out manually on paper. The second process is done with the primary aim of having a register to monitor the working habit of staff [1], as well as, monitor incoming visitors.

In the past four decades, Nigerian institutions have used and maintained the conventional system of using pen and paper to perform logging operations of the time and attendance requirements manually [2]. The manual process seeks to address three essential matters as it concerns institutions of learning: security, registry (the logging system for staff), as well as, improve Effective Employee Behavior (EEB) [3]. The manual process can be automated by utilizing the Automatic Identification and Data Capturing (AIDC) Technology first to

grant staff access and then log staff data simultaneously and automatically. To achieve this, the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) is used to tag and grant gate access to individual staff automobiles based on personal information stored and updated periodically for each staff in a remote database system. Concurrently, the second part of the process is achieved by validating information obtained through the AIDC system and for real-time record of attendance of each incoming staff [1]. The AIDC is a technology that automatically identifies objects, collects related data, and stores data directly into a computer system.

The AIDC system works with minimal human interference, and if any case of human involvement, it would be a user scanning an AIDC equipped item while the data is stored electronically in a computer system. The information associated with the object is called the identification data [4]. This data exists in different forms like images, voice, passwords, or fingerprints. The scanned data is often compared with the stored identification data in the database before providing access to the secured system. The AIDC technology consists of three principal components, namely: data encoding, machine scanning, and data decoding. The data encoding process involves the translation of alphanumeric characters into the form that can be read by the computer processor, while the machine scanning process requires a scanner that reads the encoded data and converts it into electric signals transmitted to a computer system. The data decoding is the process of converting digital data back into alphanumeric characters. The various techniques of automatic identification data capturing include Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), biometrics, magnetic stripes, Optical Character Recognition (OCR), Real-Time Locating Systems (RTLS), barcodes, smart cards, voice recognition, Electronic Article Surveillance (EAS), amongst others [4].

The RFID system is a technology that uses radio waves to transfer data between an electronic tag (transponder) attached to a particular object and the reader (antenna with receiver). The RFID system is mainly used for object identification and tracking, without necessarily direct line of sight or contact between the reader and the object. A RFID reader device sends an electromagnetic interrogation pulse to a nearby tag which triggered it, thus prompting the tag to transmit digital signals back to the reader. Usually, the transmitted digital

signal encodes the identification for the object. RFID tags can be active or passive type. Passive tags are powered by energy from the RFID reader's interrogating radio waves, while active tags are powered by external battery. Active tags typically have a larger reading range (up to hundreds of meters) from the RFID reader.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The manual process of gate access, monitoring, and logging information is time-wasting, inconvenient and very inefficient. When the information are recorded in books, the books can get lost and when they are used over a long time, it could be difficult retrieving information from them in time of crisis compared to an electronic database which can be queried at a mouse click and would generate useful result in real-time. In an attempt to address this challenge, this paper therefore, addresses these issues by developing a RFID-based system with additional Personal Identification Number (PIN)-keypad controlled which grants access to personal staff vehicles and pedestrian. In addition, it performs real-time logging using a unified approach to grant gate access, as well as, logging of time and attendance. Additionally, the use of Personal Identification Number (PIN) entry keypad for the gate access control is included after the RFID authentication to address the possibility of card theft.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Generally, RFID – based systems have been widely used for object identification, tracking and detection. Quite recently, intelligent monitoring and management of chemical warehouse was reported [5]. Management of multiple chemicals on a chemical shelf requires significant human effort which can be time-consuming. Thus, an RFID based – detector was developed which comprised of a robot equipped with RFID reader and an antenna. The robot was used for automatic scanning of the RFID – tags on the chemical bottles on the shelf. Chemical detection was achieved by measuring the received signal strength which was found to depend on the level of liquid in the bottle. In addition, the phase change between the probe carrier signal and the received radio signal by the RFID reader was used to determine the distance between the robot (RFID – detector) and the chemical bottle [5].

A RFID – based smart and intelligent ticketing system was developed using Covenant University, Ota shuttle as a case study [6]. The motivation behind the work was to minimize non - accountability of revenue generated via ticketing, as well as, reduce unnecessary argument among passengers and ticket vendors. The RFID reader was controlled by the microcontroller and placed inside the bus – shuttle, which reads the card balance from the RFID tags, deducts the fare, updates the credit, and then stores and transmits credit information to the server. Overall, the proposed system was able to integrate ticketing platform for both recharging and payment using the RFID tags [6].

The use of RFID technology for access control system was reported in [7]. The RFID reader reads the tags of authorized users which activates a magnetic door on successful

authentication. The user has to type in required password before the data from the RFID tag is accepted. A log of events (authorized and unauthorized users) is stored in the database. Only authorized users with valid RFID cards can have access to the room, since the door is protected with a magnetic door lock [7]. Other interesting applications of RFID system reported in literature include management of student attendance [8-9], real-time management of hospital patient [10], as well as, tracking of materials in manufacturing process [11]. In this work, we propose a prototype access control system for a university entrance and exit gate, using Arduino controlled - RFID systems. The approach is unique because it combines the RFID technology with a Personal Identification Number (PIN) entry for enhanced security. In addition, the details of the authorized / unauthorized users are remotely logged into a database accessible through a web interface.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The method of the project can be summarized into the following steps namely: system design, system implementation, architectural prototyping and system evaluation. The designed system (Fig. 1) consists of RFID reader placed at the entrance and exit of a gate in which RFID tags is configured for each user. An Arduino Mega is used as the primary microcontroller which integrates all the accessories such as the RFID readers, PIN pad, LCD screen, and the Servo-motors. Two additional microcontrollers (the Node-MCU microcontroller and the Arduino-Uino microcontroller) are required for modularity and for ease of control. The primary microcontroller (Arduino-Mega) has a local database containing the unique identification (UID) numbers of the allowed RFID tags. The node-MCU has a wireless card which allows data logging from the Arduino-Mega into a remote server-based database via IEEE 802.11 b/g wireless link. The server-based database was implemented using PHP-MySQL program. The flow chart of the designed system is shown in Fig. 2. The first step is initialization which engages the graphical user interface (LCD) to display the “system initialization” prompt hence, the user has a sense of communication with the underlying system. At the gate entry point, the system sets the ID (identification tag) request which prompts the reading of the Tag unique ID (UID) number. Once the UID number is obtained, its authentication is made on the Arduino-based database. In case of successful match on the Arduino-based database, the gate access authorization process is initiated. On the other hand, for non – successful match, a siren buzzer sounds briefly, and subsequently the system returns back to initialization stage. At the gate access authorization stage, a PIN request is displayed which tells the user to enter a unique PIN associated with the RFID tag. If the PIN entered is valid, then logging process is initiated, otherwise access is denied for invalid PIN, and a siren will sound momentarily. Furthermore, at the logging stage, user data such as the name and access time is immediately sent from the Arduino based database and stored in real-time on the server-based database. Once the logging is performed, the servo-motor system is initiated, which grants access to the respective user.

Fig. 1: Block Diagram of the Designed System

In summary, the designed system was made to pass through a two-step security process namely: authentication and authorization. The exit gate follows a similar procedure but using a separate microcontroller (Arduino Uno) as the brain.

The main hardware components used for the system implementation are: Arduino Mega 2560, NodeMCU, Arduino UNO, RFID Reader, RFID Tags, 20 by 4 - LCD, Keypad, buzzer, and Servo-motor. The designed system was implemented using an architectural model of Elizade University Gate – barrier system as shown in Fig. 3. The data on the RFID tag is stored on the MySQL database after gate authorization and displayed on the webpage as shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5.

V. TEST AND DISCUSSION

The system was evaluated under different scenarios:

(a) Access Control Test

Different tags were brought near the RFID reader for access control test. An unregistered RFID Tag or a valid RFID Tag with an incorrect PIN did not activate the Servo-motor and did not log the user details into the server-based MySQL database and webpage. Only a registered RFID Tag with correct PIN activates the Servo-motor and logs user's details into the database and webpage. The summary of the tests and responses are shown in Table 1.

Fig. 2: Flow chart (Operation) of the Designed System

(b) Reliability Test

The system reliability (R) of the developed system was determined from the relation in equation 1:

$$R = \frac{\text{Number of Successful Test}}{\text{Total number of Trials}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Thus, after more than 100 tests for different RFID Tags, the system reliability was obtained to be 98.052 % at the entry point, and 97.143% at the exit point. In addition, the average response time for data logging into the server-based database after gate authorization was about 150 ms.

Table 1: Result of System Reliability Test carried out on the developed system

S/ No	Card	No of Test s	PIN Input	Motor Action	Data Logging	Average Response Time (ms)
1	Valid 1	15	valid	activates	registers	150
2	Valid 2	15	valid	activates	registers	150
3	Valid 3	15	valid	activates	registers	150
4	Valid 4	15	valid	activates	registers	150
5	Valid 5	15	valid	activates	registers	150
6	Valid 6	15	valid	activates	registers	150
7	Invalid	15	no PIN	no action	no action	150

(a) Front View

(b) Right View (showing gate entry)

(c) Left View (showing exit gate)

(d) Entry RFID reader and Keypad

(e) LCD screen displays Tag UID Request

(f) LCD displays verified Tag UID

(g) LCD displays Gate Access Authorization

Fig. 3: The Prototype of the Designed System:

- (a) Front View
- (b) Right View (showing gate entry)
- (c) Left View (showing exit gate)
- (d) Entry RFID Reader and Keypad
- (e) LCD displays Tag UID Request
- (f) LCD displays verified Tag UID
- (g) LCD displays Gate Access Authorization

	id	uid	timein	fullname	gender
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	BB 22 89 09 56	2019-05-29 08:33:00	Prof Otuya	Male
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	BB 22 89 09 56	2019-05-29 08:33:43	Prof Otuya	Male
<input type="checkbox"/>	16	BB 14 61 0E	2019-05-29 08:33:24	Prof Otuya	Male
<input type="checkbox"/>	17	BB 10 11 23	2019-05-29 08:33:27	Prof Otuya	Male
<input type="checkbox"/>	19	BB 14 61 0E	2019-05-29 08:33:30	Prof Otuya	Male
<input type="checkbox"/>	20	BB 14 61 0E	2019-05-29 08:33:33	Prof Otuya	Male

Figure 4: Details of RFID tags displayed in MySQL database

ID	Full name	Card UID	Time in	Gender
1	Prof Otuya	BB 22 89 09 56	2019-05-29 08:33:00	Male
2	Prof Otuya	BB 22 89 09 56	2019-05-29 08:33:43	Male
16	Prof Otuya	BB 14 61 0E	2019-05-29 08:33:24	Male
17	Prof Otuya	BB 10 11 23	2019-05-29 08:33:27	Male
19	Prof Otuya	BB 14 61 0E	2019-05-29 08:33:30	Male
20	Prof Otuya	BB 14 61 0E	2019-05-29 08:33:33	Male

Figure 5: Details of RFID tags displayed on the webpage

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A prototype RFID based gate access control system with additional PIN entry security has been designed and implemented. The system requires three microcontrollers: primary microcontroller (Arduino Mega), Node MCU controller for data transfer to remote database and a secondary microcontroller (Arduino Uno) for the exit control. The system helps to perform two significant functions which are

access control and logging of staff data that have accessed the system. The project achieved its sole aim of ensuring the convenience and efficiency of a user logging into an institutional environment. A system reliability of 98.052 % was obtained at the entry point, and 97.143% at the exit point. Future work will include the use of Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) or Raspberry Pi for implementation of the access control on a real-life scenario.

REFERENCES

[1] Vanderbilt University. (2015, July 1).

Vanderbilt University Human Resources Policies and Procedures. Retrieved 2018, from Human Resources Division of Administration: <https://hr.vanderbilt.edu/policies/attendance-punctuality.php>.

- [2] M. Omolewa, "On the Writing of The History of Education in Nigeria", Journal of the Historical Society of Nigeria, 125-142, 1979
- [3] Glenn D. Rolfsen. (2016, May 2). EmployeeWorkHourPolicies. Retrieved 2018, fromKisi: <https://www.getkisi.com/overview/employee-work-hours-policies#5>
- [4] ElProCus. (2014, February 13). What is Automatic Identification and Data Capture Technology. Retrieved December 17, 2018, from Electronic Projects for Engineering Students: <https://www.elprocus.com/aids-what-is-automatic-identification-and-data-capture-technology/>
- [5] J. Zhao, F. Xue, & D. A. Li, "Intelligent Management of Chemical Warehouses with RFID Systems", Sensors, 20 (1), 123, 2020
- [6] O. Abayomi-Alli, M. Odusami, R. Chima, S. Misra, R. Ahuja, R. Damasevicius, & R. Maskeliunas, "Smart Ticketing for Academic Campus Shuttle Transportation System Based on RFID", In Advances in Data Sciences, Security and Applications, 237-252, March 2020, Springer, Singapore.
- [7] M. K. Shafin, K. L. Kabir, N. Hasan, I. J. Mouri, S. T. Islam, L. Ansari, M. Karim, & M. A. Hossain, "Development of an RFID based access control system in the context of Bangladesh", In IEEE International Conference on Innovations in Information, Embedded and Communication Systems (ICIIECS), Coimbatore, India, 1-5, March, 2015.
- [8] T. S. Lim, S. C. Sim, & M. M. Mansor, "RFID based attendance system", In IEEE Symposium on Industrial Electronics & Applications Vol. 2, pp. 778-782, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, October, 2009.
- [9] O. T. Arulogun, A. Olatunbosun, O. A. Fakolujo, & O. M. Olaniyi, "RFID-based students attendance management system", International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, 4(2), 1-9, 2013.
- [10] B. Chowdhury, & R. Khosla, "RFID-based hospital real-time patient management system", In 6th IEEE/ACIS International Conference on Computer and Information Science (ICIS 2007) , Melbourne, Australia, 363-368, July, 2007.
- [11] Z. Min, L. Wenfeng, W. Zhongyun, L. Bin, & R. Xia, "A RFID-based material tracking information system", In Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Automation and Logistics, Jinan, China, 2922-2926, August, 2007.